

The Impact of COVID-19 in the Tech Industry

Avornu Christian^{1*}, Prof. Jinhe Wang¹, Danquah Solomon Kwadwo Nyedu², Ibnali Issah Kulo³

¹ School of Engineering, Huzhou University, China

² Information Engineering, Huzhou University, China

³ School of Public Finance, Taxation and Public Administration, Jiangxi University of Finance and Economics, China

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Avornu Christian,

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

The past two decades were marked by the outbreaks of many viral diseases such as Ebola, Zika, Bird flu, SARS, and MERS. The world woke up to this decade with a new disease outbreak called coronavirus (COVID-19). This outbreak has thrown many sectors and disciplines into disarray. Transportation and many industries are at standstill due to shackles of lockdowns, social distancing, etc. and hence, electricity and fuel are not being used as before. One thing giving hope to some organizations and relief to people around the world is "Technology". Data was collected by gathering information from the various websites of tech industries and results of the observations show that although other sectors strive to survive during this pandemic, the tech industry continues to find means of sustaining other sectors and therefore continue to benefit more during this pandemic. Hence, the tech industry seems to observe positive impacts as compared to negative ones. This article elaborates on the major changes and benefits the tech industry has seen during this COVID-19 pandemic.

Keywords: COVID-19, TECHNOLOGY, VIRAL DISEASE OUTBREAK, TECH INDUSTRY.

Positive Impacts

1. More software development and upgrades

The tech sector has seen an increased demand for software during this covid-19 pandemic. On the forefront of solving the COVID-19 outbreak, government departments and hospitals are still searching for tools that can help teams cope with the virus and exchange knowledge with each other and with the wider world. This has caused many tech industries to develop new software or upgraded the existing ones to be able to provide services that can match up with the booming demands. South Korea and China are among many countries that have launched a Smartphone app that will help control the epidemic. All these demands for software have been attributed to an increased number of programmers and software-related workers. Therefore, these workers will make a huge sum of money during this era. Also, the lockdown has provided a conducive environment for young programmers, learners, and

researchers. Below are some of the tech industries and their software upgrade.

Table A. (1)

Software upgrade by tech industries during the COVID-19

Company Name	Focus	Software/Upgrade
Adobe	Software design tool and web conferencing.	Adobe has designed a software tool and video conferencing that allows its educational customers to request home access for students and teachers. The company has also pulled together a useful collection of content on distance learning.
Aware	Workforce governance and compliance	With many workers now operation remotely, AWARE has developed software that gives employers insights and analytics on their distributed workers.
CISCO	Videoconferencing service.	CISCO Webex has boosted the capabilities of its videoconferencing software in countries where it is available. It has scrapped the time limit on meetings and has expanded the service capability to support 100 people on a call.
LogMeIn	Videoconferencing, webinars, and device management.	LogMeIn, which offers the GoToMeeting and GoToWebinar services, has created special bundles of its products to support emergency remote working. As well as supporting virtual meetings.
Alipay	Online Payment Platform	The platform has been upgraded with a health code system. The color of the health code determines whether you have visited a high-risk area within the last 14 days.

2. Tech industries offering free services as a benefit in disguise.

Some of the Tech industries have wisely scored some points by making some of their services available for free during this era. This will first and foremost help them market their product to the world and secondly result in enrolling more businesses onto their platform. After the free service period is over, these tech industries begin to make a lot of money as many companies are bound to still use the services offered. Below are some of these tech industries.

Table B.(1)

Some Tech Industries offered free services.

Company Name	Focus	Free Offer
NetApp	Cloud storage.	NetApp offered 25 terabytes of storage on Google Cloud for 90 days for free to teams grappling with the consequences of the pandemic.
Yahoo	Website creation and management.	Yahoo Small Business is offering a free package of services that lets companies do things like create a web presence and manage email accounts.
Enable	Rebate-management software.	One of the company's essential packages which allows users to set up deals and creates a central repository is being offered free during this pandemic.
GITHUB	Code-repository service.	GitHub made its private code repository for an unlimited number of collaborators for free. All of the platform's core features are now accessible for nothing.
Google	Videoconferencing service and online	Google cloud announced free access to its advanced Hangouts Meet videoconferencing capabilities for all customers of its G-Suite and education services. This enables calls of up to 250 people and also allows meetings to be recorded and saved on Google Drive.
Grammarly	Digital Writing tools	Grammarly has given free access to NGO and nonprofit organizations during this pandemic era. This includes its premium-level writing suggestions and integration with key workplace tools.
Hyper Proof	Privacy-management software.	Hyperproof is given out its software for free to help organizations stay compliant with privacy regimes in Europe.
IBM	Cloud-based business productivity and educational services.	Big Blue offered free 90 days access to services such as IBM Aspera, its service for high-speed file-sharing and team collaboration, and its IBM Sterling supply-chain management service.

JFrog	Develops Tools	JFrog has provided free DevOps technology to organizations whose projects are actively researching and fighting COVID-19.
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3. Social media platforms.

Social media owners have witnessed a great positive impact during the pandemic. Google Hangouts, WhatsApp Video call, Zoom, Microsoft Teams, Instagram, Twitter, Facebook, etc. are some of the social media platforms the has seen a high number of subscriptions during this pandemic. A study of people’s engagement on the internet and social media collected from July 2019 - 2020 indicated a 10.5% increase of active social media users (2). Instagram reported a 70% increase in viewers of live videos from February to March when lockdown measures began. The more people stay on social media, the more adverts are run and the more money generated for owners of these social media platforms.

4. Telecommunication Boost

There have also been a lot of positive impacts in the telecommunication sector. First and foremost, more income as more data is being used during this era. Secondly, more businesses are now procuring devices, setting up a resilient, scalable, and stable network, disaster recovery system, and internet protection for the purpose of flexible remote working. All these purchases create a lot of income for the telecom sector. As never before, the need for ever-faster access to data and automation has intensified the focus on network equipment and communications, speeding up 5G network implementations and 5G equipment adoption.

5. Improved AI Technologies

Several countries facing the lockdown have invested in Artificial Intelligence (AI) technology solutions. China uses drones attached to thermal sensors to detect coronavirus symptoms and provide urgent medical support. The government has introduced a chatbot in Australia to keep people up-to-date with the situation and answer their questions so that they can minimize the spread of false information and avoid the fear that could be generated in the public. Robots are used in China and other countries to deliver food to infected patients to reduces too much contact with infected persons.

AI measures have been put in place for forecasting the spread of viruses and developing early warning systems by extracting information from social media platforms, calls, news sites, etc. in other to provide useful information about vulnerable regions and other possible predictions.

Researchers have developed a deep learning model called COVID-19 Detection Neural Network, for differentiating between COVID-19 and community-acquired pneumonia based on visual 2D and 3D features extracted from a volumetric chest CT scan. (3)

COVID-19 vaccine has been designed using reverse vaccinology and machine learning. For the first time, vaccines have been designed using AI technology. Researchers predicted possible vaccine candidates for

COVID-19 using the Vaxign reverse vaccinology-machine learning platform that relied on supervised classification models.

All these new discoveries have improved the current level of AI in the tech industry as a whole.

6. More companies adopting remote work technology

More companies, especially small business has shifted from the traditional way of doing business to remote working. This has been of many benefits to more tech industries as they recording several small businesses using their platforms as a means of survival.

Also, Security software has seen third-order benefits from a growing remote workforce. IT expenses on security software have increased as organizations battle to secure endpoint, especially cloud-based tools, log management, and VPNs. Therefore, is predicted that environmental, social, and economic factors, along with developments in technology such as 5G, will probably push more and more businesses to fully adopt "the remote workplace" in the next few years.

Another benefit the tech industry has seen as a result of remote working is the high demand for hardware tools. A lot of enterprises are placing large orders for laptops and mobile devices to support employees now working from home.

Remote working has also caused an increase in cloud computing as businesses are keen to adopt this new cloud-based model of working as they realize increased productivity with less investment in office space. This, in turn, is accelerating the pace at which many organizations are being pushed to embrace remote work.

7. A switch to digital twin by tech companies.

A digital twin is a technology that makes use of the virtual representation of a real-world product or asset. Digital twins are vital to improving situational awareness and allowing most companies to test future scenarios that can enhance asset performance and proactively anticipate maintenance faults.

As travel restrictions and social distancing requirements limit the number of experts and technicians who can physically visit industrial sites, most tech industries have adopted digital twine technology as one way to increase transparency into inaccessible systems, which can act as a living and learning virtual model of a real asset.

Negative Impacts

Amidst the many positive impacts, the tech industry has seen a few negative ones during this pandemic. Firstly, a lot of things have been rushed to meet the increasing demands in such a way that if care is not taken, some systems may fail in the mare future. Some systems may also suffer security threats as much time was not spent on testing before deployment. Distribution of raw materials such as aluminum, copper, and other hardware devices, needed by the telecommunication sector for full deployment of remote working has been slowed down in some cities due to lockdowns and slow shipment.

Way forward after the pandemic.

The tech industry has proven that everything is feasible in any situation. More businesses became smarter, more cities have ended up being smarter and life has become normal without outdoor events. Plenty of workers who don't seem to be glued to working remotely have lent to do so. Companies that failed to believe their business could solely rely on remote working now have confidence in the system. Students and teachers have no choice but to adapt to the new trend and there seems to be a concrete alternative during pandemics. Also, all software developed and upgraded during this pandemic has come to stay. Hence should an endemic like COVID-19 comes up within the near future, its negative impact on other organization won't be that much compared to previous. These testify that the tech industry is anticipated to boom up than before after the pandemic.

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Christian Avornu completed his Bachelor's of Science Degree in Computer Science at the University of Cape-Coast, Ghana. Presently, he is pursuing Masters in Intelligent Equipment Automation Technology at Huzhou University and also an Intern at Zhejiang Haoyang New Science and Technology Ltd, China. His current research area includes Data Fusion for Intelligent Manufacturing.

Name: Avornu Christian (Main Author)
Institution: Huzhou University
Department: School of Engineering
Major: Masters in Intelligent Equipment Automation Technology
Email: cavornu@yahoo.com

Name: Prof. Jinhe Wang (Co Author)
Institution: Huzhou University
Department: School of Engineering
Major: Smart Manufacturing
Email: 179911980@qq.com

Name: Danquah Solomon Kwadwo Nyedu (Co Author)
Institution: Huzhou University
Department: Information Engineering
Major: MSc. E-Commerce Technology
Email: solodanq@gmail.com

Name: Ibnali Issah Kulo (Co Author)
Institution: Jiangxi University of Finance and Economics
Department: School of Public finance, Taxation and Public Administration
Major: International Masters in Public Administration
Email: kuloissah969@gmail.com

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